

re-late – re-use – re-vise

Large Language Models and Their Potential for Variant and Intertextuality Studies in the Digital Humanities

Thursday, 4th December 2025, 9:00–16:45

Jura-Soyfer-Saal, Hofburg, Batthyanyntiege, 1010 Wien

Organized by Gerrit Brüning, Janis Pagel, Axel Pichler, Felix Schenke and Gabriel Viehhauser in cooperation with the DHd-AG Angewandte Generative KI in den Digitalen Geisteswissenschaften (AGKI-DH). The project is financed by CLARIAH-AT with support from the BMFWF and with support from the DHd. If you plan to attend, please send a short notice to Gabriel Viehhauser at gabriel.viehhauser@univie.ac.at

9:00–9:20

Welcome and Introduction

Gabriel Viehhauser (Universität Wien)

Section 1

9:20–9:55

Making Sense of Versions: A Collaborative Model of Textual Variation

Beatrice Nava (Universität Wien) / Elli Bleeker (KNAW Amsterdam)

9:55–10:30

Visualising Complex Textual Variants with the Interactive Tool LERA

Marcus Pöckelmann (Freie Universität Berlin)

Coffee Break

10:30–10:45

Section 2

10:45–11:20

Multilingual Text Alignment and Editing Practices: The COMUTE Project

Sandra Balck / Brigitte Grote (Freie Universität Berlin)

11:20–11:55

Analysing Literary Variants and Versioning: (How) Can LLMs Help?

Gerrit Brüning / Felix Schenke (Klassik Stiftung Weimar)

Lunch Break

11:55–13:30

Section 3

13:30–14:05

Tracing Textual Genesis Through Parts-of-Speech-Tagging of Selected Poems by Friederike Mayröcker

Johanna Unterholzner (ÖAW Wien)

14:05–14:40

Evaluation-Oriented Generation of Text-Genetic Interpretations from Non-Digital Editions

Axel Pichler (Universität Wien)

Coffee Break

14:40–14:55

Section 4

14:55–15:30

Challenges in Automatic Identification of Indirect Quotations Between Scholarly Texts and Literary Works

Robert Jäschke / Frederik Arnold (Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin)

15:30–16:05

Exploring Gender References in Wertheriaden Through Network Analysis

Janis Pagel (Universität zu Köln) / Marie Flüh (Universität Hamburg)

16:05–16:40

How to Align Medieval Prose Texts and Other Impossibilities

Gabriel Viehhauser (Universität Wien)

16:40–16:45

Farewell

Abstracts & Infos:

<https://tinyurl.com/3uema9hw>

